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Data Format:

Most data are in open format.

Fluorescence data (OPJ) can be read in Origin Viewer (<https://www.originlab.com/viewer/>).

CLSM file (lif) can be read in FIJI/ImageJ (<https://fiji.sc/>).

FLIM data can be read in SymPhoTime software (Picoquant).

IXM-C (high content) data can be read in MetaExpress (<https://www.moleculardevices.com>)